

Guidelines on Application of Web Accessibility

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These accessibility guidelines offer a structured and supportive reference to help teams consider and incorporate accessibility throughout the lifecycle of Base4NFDI basic services, from planning and design to development, testing, and maintenance. While not a substitute for legal consultation or formal compliance checks, the document serves as a practical resource to guide inclusive design decisions, encourage alignment with relevant standards, and promote better usability for all users, including those with disabilities.

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1. Introduction

Ensuring accessibility in digital services is both a legal requirement and an ethical imperative. For services supported by [Base4NFDI](#), which are publicly funded through [the German Research Foundation \(DFG\)](#), accessibility falls under the legal framework of the [Behindertengleichstellungsgesetz \(BGG\)](#) and its implementing regulation, [Barrierefreie-Informationstechnik-Verordnung \(BITV\) 2.0](#). These laws ensure that public digital offerings are usable for people with disabilities.

In addition, this guideline also takes into account the [Barrierefreiheitsstärkungsgesetz \(BFSG\)](#), which implements the [European Accessibility Act \(EAA\)](#). The BFSG, now fully in effect since **June 28, 2025**, introduces accessibility obligations for a broader range of digital products and services, including those in the private sector and consumer-facing domains. Like the BGG and BITV 2.0, the BFSG mandates compliance with the [Web Content Accessibility Guidelines \(WCAG\) 2.1](#), Level AA, as the technical minimum standard for digital accessibility.

This document therefore supports Base4NFDI services in:

- Understanding and complying with **BGG/BITV 2.0** obligations,
- Preparing for broader European standards under the **BFSG/EAA**,
- Embedding accessibility throughout the service development lifecycle,
- Aligning with **Open Science** and **FAIR** principles.

By offering adaptable, forward-looking guidance, this document helps service teams meet current legal expectations while building toward sustainable and inclusive digital platforms.

1.1 Purpose of the Guidelines

The primary goal of this guideline is to help basic services embed accessibility in their design and development processes. This ensures:

- **Compliance** with BGG/BITV 2.0 and alignment with WCAG 2.1 AA standards,
- **Readiness** for future EU-wide regulations under the BFSG,
- **Improved usability** and inclusivity for users with disabilities,
- **Reduced cost** through early accessibility integration (“accessibility by design”),
- **Greater sustainability and outreach** of digital research infrastructure.

Following WCAG 2.1 Level AA is essential for compliance with Germany’s national accessibility standards (BITV 2.0) and aligns with the forthcoming EU accessibility regulations (BFSG). BITV 2.0 requires adherence to WCAG 2.1 Level AA for publicly funded services, while WCAG 2.1 itself provides a widely recognized, future-proof technical standard that underpins both national and European accessibility frameworks.

1.2 Target Audience

This guideline is intended for a wide range of stakeholders involved in the development, management, and governance of Base4NFDI services, including:

- **Developers and technical teams:** Those responsible for coding and designing accessible digital services.
- **Service managers and project leads:** Individuals overseeing service development and ensuring compliance with accessibility requirements.
- **Researchers and contributors:** Those who develop or use Base4NFDI services and need to understand accessibility implications.
- **Legal and policy experts:** Professionals guiding accessibility compliance, particularly concerning BFG and European regulations.
- **Funding bodies and decision-makers:** Organizations that support Base4NFDI services and encourage accessibility as part of their policies.

By engaging these groups, the guideline promotes a collaborative approach to accessibility.

1.3 Scope and Applicability

This guideline focuses on accessibility in basic services supported by Base4NFDI, particularly those intended for broad or public use. Key considerations include:

- **Legal compliance:** Services must comply with BGG/BITV 2.0, especially if publicly funded and intended for general users. Even if a service is still in development, accessibility planning should begin early.
- **Forward alignment with BFG:** While the BFG is not currently binding for all Base4NFDI services, it introduces accessibility requirements for digital services that are public-facing and consumer-oriented. These requirements became legally effective on **June 28, 2025**. As basic services continue to mature and are potentially offered to broader user groups, they may increasingly fall within the scope of the BFG. Anticipating this possibility helps ensure legal preparedness and alignment with evolving EU-wide accessibility standards.
- **Best practices:** Accessibility enhances usability, discoverability, and long-term impact regardless of a service's legal obligations.
- **Development stages:** Accessibility can and should be introduced incrementally, aligned with each project's development phase, from planning and design to deployment and iteration.

1.4 Timeline

While **BGG/BITV 2.0** already applies to DFG-funded services, the **BFSG** introduced a new layer of accessibility regulation as of **June 28, 2025**, primarily targeting private-sector and consumer-facing digital services.

Key Milestones:

- **Now–Mid 2025:** Training, assessments, design adaptation, and early implementation of WCAG 2.1 AA standards.
- **June 28, 2025:** The BFSG came into effect, serving as a key point of reference for services that are planning for future public release or broader user access.
- **Post-2025:** Continuous monitoring of compliance under BGG and alignment with broader EU standards.

Pro Tip: It's significantly more cost-effective and technically feasible to build accessibility into a product from the start than to retrofit it later. "Accessibility by design" ensures a smoother rollout and fewer last-minute surprises.

2. Legal and Practical Relevance of Accessibility

Accessibility is no longer optional; it is a critical aspect of how digital services are designed, delivered, and maintained. It is important not only for legal compliance, but also for creating better user experiences and fulfilling ethical responsibilities. For basic services supported by Base4NFDI, understanding the evolving regulatory landscape and the broader value of accessibility can help teams future-proof their platforms and serve all users more effectively.

This chapter explains the key legal requirements, outlines what different teams need to know about compliance, and highlights why accessibility is about more than just ticking boxes; it is about quality, inclusivity, and long-term sustainability.

2.1 Overview of the BGG, BFSG, and The EAA

Accessibility is increasingly mandated by law in Europe. In Germany, the **Barrierefreiheitsstärkungsgesetz (BFSG)**, which came into full effect on June 28, 2025, implements the European Accessibility Act (EAA) at the national level. These regulations require that digital products and services, such as websites, mobile applications, and software, are accessible to everyone, including people with disabilities.

The **BFSG** applies to a wide range of digital services, especially those offered by public institutions or services with a broad user base, including Base4NFDI services. The **BFSG** does not create new technical standards but refers to existing international guidelines, most notably the **WCAG 2.1, Level AA**. These guidelines provide practical, well-documented advice on making digital content more readable, navigable, and interactive for a wide range of users.

In parallel, the **BGG** outlines accessibility requirements for services provided by public institutions and aims to guarantee equal participation for individuals with disabilities across all areas of life, including digital services. Since basic services are publicly funded, ultimately through the DFG, they are expected to align with accessibility standards such as those outlined in the **BGG** and, where applicable, the **BFSG**. While not all basic services currently fall under the strict legal scope of the BFSG, especially in early or internal phases, proactively adopting these standards ensures legal preparedness, improves inclusivity, and aligns with public funding expectations and EU-wide accessibility goals.

Comparison of BGG and BFSG Accessibility Goals & Obligations

BGG is based on anti-discrimination law. Its main goal is to ensure equality and inclusion for people with disabilities, especially in the public sector. It applies to public institutions and publicly funded services, like many Base4NFDI services, and is supported by technical standards in BITV 2.0, which mandates compliance with WCAG 2.1 AA.

BFSG, on the other hand, is derived from market regulation. It implements the European Accessibility Act (EU Directive 2019/882) and focuses on ensuring that digital and consumer services, including those in the private sector, are accessible to everyone. Now fully applicable as of June 28, 2025, the BFSG also uses WCAG 2.1 AA as its technical benchmark for accessibility.

Overview Table: BGG vs. BFSG

Aspect	BGG (Behindertengleichstellungsgesetz)	BFSG (Barrierefreiheitsstärkungsgesetz)
Legal Basis - focus of the law	Anti-discrimination / Equal Rights Law	Market Regulation - EU Accessibility Act (Directive 2019/882)
Sector Focus	Public sector (government & publicly funded services)	Public-facing products & services, including private sector

Purpose	Ensure equal access and participation for people with disabilities	Ensure accessibility in consumer and digital markets
Applies To	Public institutions and DFG-funded projects	Digital services/products offered to consumers (e.g. apps, e-books)
Relevance to Base4NFDI	Applies because services are publicly funded via DFG	May apply in future as services become public-facing or consumer-like
Technical Minimum Standard	WCAG 2.1 Level AA via BITV 2.0	WCAG 2.1 Level AA
Enforcement	Federal Inclusion Authority / BITV 2.0 enforcement	Market surveillance authorities from June 2025

Note: By following WCAG 2.1 Level AA, services ensure compliance with both BGG/BITV 2.0 and future BFG requirements.

In conclusion, both the BGG and BFG establish a legal foundation for digital accessibility in Germany, BGG focusing on inclusivity in the public sector, and BFG extending obligations to broader, consumer-facing digital services under EU law. Despite their different scopes, both frameworks rely on WCAG 2.1 Level AA as the common technical standard. For Base4NFDI services, which are publicly funded and may eventually reach broader user groups, aligning with WCAG 2.1 AA not only ensures legal preparedness but also promotes an inclusive, sustainable, and user-friendly digital infrastructure

2.2 Responsibilities, Enforcement, and Compliance

Accessibility compliance under frameworks such as the BGG and the upcoming BFG is not limited to a single role or stage; it requires coordinated attention across technical, managerial, and strategic levels. Responsibility is distributed across development teams,

service owners, and institutional stakeholders who must ensure that accessibility is addressed from planning through deployment.

While national authorities are responsible for enforcement through mechanisms like audits or user-initiated complaints, the accountability for meeting requirements lies with the organizations providing the services. Especially for public-facing or widely used digital services, accessibility is a foundational quality criterion. Recognizing accessibility as part of compliance and risk management contributes to better governance and strengthens trust in digital research infrastructure.

Pro Tip: So, who needs to do what? If your service will be accessed by the public or is intended for general use, it is good to start planning for compliance early. This applies whether you are a developer, project manager, or team lead.

- Public-facing services will fall under BFGS regulation and will be legally required to meet accessibility standards.
- Enforcement is handled by national authorities; there may be audits, spot checks, or requirements to respond to user complaints about accessibility barriers.
- Non-compliance could result in mandatory remediation actions or reputational damage.

But this is not just about rules. Planning for accessibility from the beginning will save time and money in the long run and help you avoid rushed, last-minute fixes.

Even if your service isn't directly regulated, applying these standards now helps ensure:

- you are ready if regulations expand,
- you meet funder expectations (e.g., DFG's open science values),
- and you offer a better experience for *all* users.

2.3 Broader Impact: Ethics, Usability, and Social Open Science

Accessibility is not just a legal checklist; it is about how you treat your users.

When you build inclusively, you create digital services that are:

- ethically grounded, ensuring equal access to information and tools,
- usable by more people, including those with cognitive, physical, visual, or situational limitations,

- aligned with Open Science values, which emphasize transparency, participation, and equity.

Improved accessibility also benefits users who might not identify as having a disability:

- older users navigating complex interfaces,
- people accessing your service on mobile devices,
- researchers using assistive technologies due to temporary injuries or environmental factors.

In the context of basic services, where collaboration, sustainability, and public funding are central, accessibility reflects your commitment to community and research integrity. By making your services more accessible, you contribute to strengthening the entire ecosystem and foster innovation through broader participation, ensuring that all users, regardless of their abilities, can engage fully.

3. WCAG 2.1 AA: Key Requirements for Services

The Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.1 are intended to improve the accessibility and usability of digital content for all users. The guidelines are built around four fundamental principles, which serve as the foundation for all success criteria:

- 1) **Perceivable**
- 2) **Operable**
- 3) **Understandable**
- 4) **Robust**

These principles structure the WCAG 2.1 and will be explained in more detail in the following presentation of the individual criteria.

In the WCAG 2.1 all criteria are assigned to one of the conformance levels A, AA or AAA, with A being the most important criteria for accessibility. If a success criterion is assigned to conformance level A, this usually means that failure to meet the success criterion excludes at least one user group from use. Success criteria at the medium conformance level AA represent further important requirements and success criteria at the highest conformance level AAA contain further evaluation options for the accessibility of a website.

Accessibility laws in Germany require compliance with WCAG up to Level AA. It is generally recommended to aim for Level AAA compliance, but it is often not possible to meet all Level AAA criteria, as some of the success criteria cannot be applied to all types of content.

Guideline 1: Perceivable

Information and user interface components must be presentable to users in ways they can perceive.

Guideline 1.1: Text Alternatives

Provide text alternatives for any non-text content so that it can be changed into other forms people need, such as large print, braille, speech, symbols or simpler language.

1.1.1 [Text Alternatives for Non-Text Content](#)

What is affected and why?

Non-text elements are: graphic control elements, pictures, graphics, image maps and informative audio elements. Non-text elements are not accessible for blind users and therefore an accessible alternative must be provided.

How is the criterion met?

The text alternative takes the place of a control element, graphic etc. or is intended to replace the elements.

a) Graphic control elements

The alternative texts for control elements (e.g. icons or logos) or teaser images should describe the target of the link. Alternative texts for graphic buttons should describe the action that the button triggers. If image maps are used, their areas (area elements) should have meaningful alternative texts.

The alternative text describes the purpose, not the appearance of the element (like here “Newsletter” instead of “Envelope”).

Example:

b) Graphics and pictures

Non-linked information-oriented graphics and images must be provided with alternative texts. The alt attribute replaces the content as concisely as possible, while the title attribute is intended for additional (non-essential) information and the longdesc attribute is for detailed descriptions. The alternative texts replace the image, so they should (if possible) fulfill the same task as the image. In case of font graphics, the text alternative should repeat the text of the font graphic. In the case of images or similar elements that focus on a specific sensory experience, a brief description of the object depicted is usually sufficient.

Example:

alt="The Rt Hon Sir Keir

Starmer KCB KC MP"

More detailed explanations may be required for diagrams or technical drawings. Alternative texts are not suitable for this; if possible, they should not exceed 80 characters. The alternative text then only states what is shown and where (for example: "Details in the following text"), the explanation is in the context of the image.

Logo-type elements in which graphics and text are combined are almost never to be regarded as mere decorative graphics and therefore require alternative text that states that a symbol, sign or logo is depicted and reflects the meaning of the symbol or sign.

Example:

alt="Logo: Federal Ministry of the Interior and Community"

alt="Logo: Federal Ministry of the

Interior and Community"

When dealing with non-linked, information-bearing icons, it is important to consider the type of icons used and whether they include accompanying text. In the case of icon fonts—typefaces that contain symbols instead of letters—it is not possible to provide a text alternative using the alt attribute. Apart from this, if it is an information-bearing icon without visible text (stand-alone icon), there should be a text alternative. This can be text, for example, which is hidden using a suitable method like HTML-Tags (display:none should not be used) or which is provided via an Accessible Rich Internet Applications (ARIA)-label. Since the text replaces the image, the icon itself should be hidden from screen readers using an appropriate technique (e.g. aria-hidden="true").

Example:

The picture shows an icon that stands for sign language and is hidden with ARIA-attribute.

The alt attribute must remain empty for purely decorative images, so that it is ignored by assistive technologies.

Example:

Guideline 1.2: Time-based Media

Provide alternatives for time-based media.

1.2.1 [Audio-only and Video-only \(Prerecorded\)](#)

What is affected and why?

Audio files and silent video files that convey information must be provided with equivalent media alternatives - unless they are already media alternatives for text. Audio files (e.g. audio podcasts) are not or only partially accessible for hearing-impaired users, which is why they require transcription. Silent video files (such as a film or animation sequence that shows how to assemble a device without audio commentary) are not available to blind and visually impaired users. They therefore need a fully-fledged media alternative (text or audio file).

How is the criterion met?

For audio files a transcript is necessary, that covers the same content as the audio files. In the case of audio files with different voices, the person speaking is identified in the transcription.

For video files a media alternative that conveys the same information as the visual content should be provided. This can be a text version (directly or via a link), an alternative audio track or an additional audio file. The alternative or a meaningful link to it should be provided in the direct context of the audio or video file.

Example:

The picture shows a video of the Berlin Senate Chancellery, where the descriptions of the video content is provided below the video.

Die Senatskanzlei Berlin stellt sich vor

Das Video kann in verschiedenen Größen heruntergeladen werden, über das Download-Symbol am rechten oberen Bildrand.

Video-Inhalt zum Nachlesen: Vorstellung

Die Senatskanzlei ist der Verwaltungsstab des Regierenden Bürgermeisters von Berlin. Sie unterstützt ihn bei der Planung und Steuerung der Berliner Landespolitik.

Zu ihren Aufgaben gehören die politische Koordination der Senatsarbeit, die Zusammenarbeit mit dem Bund und den anderen Bundesländern, die Presse- und Informationsarbeit sowie die Vertretung Berlins nach außen einschließlich der Beziehungen zu den Partnerstädten in aller Welt.

1.2.2 [Captions \(Prerecorded\)](#)

What is affected and why?

If the audio track of a recorded video contains information, subtitles must be provided as an alternative. As a rule, films cannot be understood without the sound. Therefore, the content of the soundtrack must be provided in subtitles for people with hearing impairments. Subtitles can also be helpful for other users, for example for people who are not familiar with the language of the film.

How is the criterion met?

Subtitles should be automatically displayed or optionally switched on in parallel with the video, so that it corresponds to the audible content. This may include an indication of who is speaking and meaningful sound events (such as information-carrying noises, laughter, applause). Alternatively, it is also valid if there is a complete text alternative (transcription) or a clearly labeled link to a complete text alternative in the immediate context of the video.

Example:

1.2.3 [Audio Description or Media Alternative \(Prerecorded\)](#)

What is affected and why?

This ensures that people who are blind or visually impaired can access visual content in synchronized media like videos. There are two ways to meet it. The first is audio description, which adds spoken explanations of key visual details—such as actions, settings, and text on screen—during natural pauses in dialogue. The second is a text alternative that fully describes all visual and audio content, like a script or book. Unlike audio description, it isn't limited to pauses and includes detailed descriptions of scenes, actions, facial expressions, background sounds, and full dialogue transcripts, all in the same order as the original media. If the media includes interaction (e.g. pressing a button), the text version must offer the same functionality through links or similar features. This approach gives a more complete and flexible experience than audio description alone.

How is the criterion met?

An alternative for time-based media or audio description of the prerecorded video content is provided for synchronized media, except when the media is a media alternative for text and is clearly labeled as such.

Example:

This [video](#) by Aktion Mensch uses an audio description (in German).

1.2.4 [Captions \(Live\)](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to enable people who are deaf or hard of hearing to watch *real-time* presentations. Captions provide the part of the content available via the audio track. Captions not only include dialogue, but also identify who is speaking and notate sound effects and other significant audio.

How is the criterion met?

Captions are provided for all live audio content in synchronized media.

1.2.5 [Audio Description \(Prerecorded\)](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to provide people who are blind or visually impaired access to the visual information in a synchronized media presentation in the same human language as the video or page on which it appears. The audio description augments the audio portion of the presentation with the information needed when the video portion is not available. During existing pauses in dialogue, audio description provides information about actions, characters, scene changes, and on-screen text that are important and are not described or spoken in the main soundtrack. People who are blind or have low vision, as well as those with cognitive limitations who have difficulty interpreting visually what is happening benefit from audio description of visual information.

How is the criterion met?

Audio description is provided for all prerecorded video content in synchronized media.

Note: 1.2.3, 1.2.5, and 1.2.8 overlap somewhat with each other. This is to give the author some choice at the minimum conformance level, and to provide additional requirements at higher levels. At Level A in success criterion 1.2.3, authors do have the choice of providing either an audio description or a full text alternative. If they wish to conform at Level AA, under success criterion 1.2.5 authors must provide an audio description - a requirement already met if they chose that alternative for 1.2.3, otherwise an additional requirement.

Guideline 1.3: Adaptable

Create content that can be presented in different ways (e.g. simpler layout) without losing information or structure.

1.3.1 [Info and Relation](#)

What is affected and why?

Website content is visualized through headings, tables, lists, different text styles, weights, and so on. Users who cannot use this visual organization, for example, because they are blind or can only see a small section of the page, are dependent on the structure being accessible and usable independently of the display on the screen. A programmatically accessible structure makes it easier to navigate and understand the page, for example by jumping from heading to heading.

How is the criterion met?

Information about content structure and relationships is available, including headlines, lists, citations, and tables.

a) Headings

Headings must be properly marked using HTML structural elements or equivalent ARIA roles and attributes (h1 followed by h2 followed by h3, etc., or corresponding ARIA attributes on elements with role="heading") to reflect the structure of the page content. Omitting hierarchy levels is not inherently incorrect as long as the overall heading sequence remains logical.

Example:

The picture shows a heading of the second hierarchy level with a paragraph beneath it.

[H2] **The underlying principle of German economic policy** [/H2]

[P] The social market economy lays the basis for economic and social security and a good quality of life in Germany and in Europe. It has been and still is a guarantor of growth and prosperity for all. [/P]

b) Lists

All lists, including menus, must be marked with HTML structural elements for lists (ul, ol, and so on). The ol element is used when the list is ordered, and the ul element is used when the list is unordered. Description lists (dl) are used to group name-value pairs of information, for example: terms and definitions or questions and answers.

Example:

The picture shows the structural elements of an unordered list.

```
<ul>  
  ■ <li>Border checks at Germany's Schengen borders</li>  
  ■ <li>Patrols along the internal borders, on trains and on railway property</li>  
  ■ <li>Various forms of cooperation in the border regions between the Federal Police, the state police forces and the Federal Customs Administration, such as joint investigation teams and police and customs cooperation centres</li>  
  ■ <li>Effective investigation and situation analysis by the Federal Police, Federal Criminal Police Office (BKA) and responsible state-level authorities</li>  
  ■ <li>Comprehensive, interministerial and interagency analysis of irregular migration, migrant smuggling and related crime at the Joint Centre for Analysis and Strategy on Illegal Migration (GASIM) with the participation of the Federal Police, BKA, BAMF, BND, BfV, the Federal Foreign Office and the Federal Customs Administration unit responsible for enforcing the law on illegal employment and benefit fraud</li>  
</ul>
```

c) Quotations

Quotations that are formulated as independent sections must be marked with blockquote throughout.

Example:

The first picture shows a quotation and the following picture show the corresponding label in the source code.

“We are making Germany stronger, also when it comes to bolstering our democracy – against extremist incitement and populist lies, against Russian propaganda and the enemies of democracy.”

NANCY FAESER, FEDERAL MINISTER OF THE INTERIOR AND COMMUNITY

```

<h2 class="aural">quote:</h2>
<div class="c-quote__container">
  <blockquote class="c-quote__bq">
    <span class="small">...</span>
  </blockquote>
  <div class="c-quote__add-content c-quote__add-content--no-image">...</div>
</div>

```

d) Highlighting and paragraphs

Text paragraphs are marked with suitable paragraph elements (p is preferred, but div is permitted). However, text paragraphs should not be wrapped using double
-elements or spaces to create columns. Strong or em is used for semantic highlighting in the text.

Example:

[P] [STRONG] International Energy Agency recommends Germany to use energy transition as a driver of energy security and economic competitiveness [/STRONG] [/P]

[P] 09/04/2025 PRESS RELEASE [/P]

e) Tables

Tables must be labeled with table and table headings with th or the corresponding ARIA roles. The table must also have a clear structure, e.g. by using meaningful headings to which the columns and rows can be assigned. Tables are also often used for layout purposes. This can be recognized by empty columns or rows, for example, and must be avoided.

Example:

The picture shows the structural elements of a table.

<table summary="Regierungsentwurf 2025">		
<th> Einzelplan	<th> Betrag (in Tausend Euro)	<th> Anteil
<td> Bundesministerium für Arbeit und Soziales	<td> 179.257.094	<td> 36,69%
<td> Bundesministerium der Verteidigung	<td> 53.250.000	<td> 10,9%
<td> Bundesministerium für Digitales und Verkehr	<td> 49.667.947	<td> 10,17%
<td> Allgemeine Finanzverwaltung	<td> 46.170.579	<td> 9,45%

1.3.2 [Meaningful Sequence](#)

What is affected and why?

Content should be presented in a meaningful and useful order, regardless of the presentation. Content that belongs together (such as a headline and the corresponding content below it) should not be torn apart. In addition, content that does not meet this success criterion may confuse or disorient users when assistive technology reads the content in the wrong order or when alternate style sheets or other formatting changes are applied.

How is the criterion met?

Usually, the visual order of the page elements should match the order in the source text. Problems often arise here when using CSS layout technology grid. In some cases, deliberate deviations from the visual order may be acceptable, for example, if the date of the news item is visually above the headline in a news section, but follows it in the reading order. The criterion for evaluation is always that the content is understandable in the order in which it is displayed. Moreover, dynamic content that is visually hidden in the initial state should also be hidden for screen readers so that it does not disrupt the reading sequence.

Example:

The first picture shows the content with an active CSS styling.

Publications

Presentations on Base4NFDI and the basic services

- [Presentation materials of Base4NFDI \(03/2025\)](#). **new!** Last update: March 2025.
- [Overview of current basic services](#). **new!** Last update: Jan 2025
- [Base4NFDI - Creating NFDI-wide basic services in a world of specific domains](#). 14.09.2023, CoRDI 2023
- [Presentation materials from the proposal](#). Last update: 30.08.2023

Base4NFDI Workshops on the integration of basic services into NFDI Consortia

- [Integration Phase Workshop III: Materials](#). Workshop held in March 2025. Includes information on how to get involved with the basic services.
- [Integration Phase Workshop I: Summary](#). Workshop held in April 2024.

Base4NFDI project proposal

- [Base4NFDI - Basic Services for NFDI](#). V2. 01.12.2023

The second picture shows that the content has the same order when CSS is turned off.

Publications

Presentations on Base4NFDI and the basic services

- [Presentation materials of Base4NFDI \(03/2025\)](#), new! Last update: March 2025.
- [Overview of current basic services](#), new! Last update: Jan 2025
- [Base4NFDI - Creating NFDI-wide basic services in a world of specific domains](#), 14.09.2023, CoRDI 2023
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Base4NFDI project proposal

- [Base4NFDI - Basic Services for NFDI](#), V2, 01.12.2023

1.3.3 [Sensory Characteristics](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to ensure that all users can access instructions for using the content, even when they cannot perceive shape or size or use information about spatial location or orientation. Some content relies on knowledge of the shape or position of objects that are not available from the structure of the content (for example, "round button" or "button to the right"). Some users with disabilities are not able to perceive shape or position due to the nature of the assistive technologies they use. This success criterion requires that additional information be provided to clarify instructions that are dependent on this kind of information.

How is the criterion met?

Instructions provided for understanding and operating content do not rely solely on sensory characteristics of components such as shape, color, size, visual location, orientation, or sound.

Example:

The following layout places a button in the lower right corner and indicates it by position. An indication of the text label clarifies which button to use for users for whom the position is not meaningful.

Complete the form and then press the lower-right (*sign up*) button.

Your name

Your email address

Cancel

Sign up

1.3.4 [Orientation](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to ensure that content displays in the orientation (portrait or landscape) preferred by the user. Some websites and applications automatically set and restrict the screen to a particular display orientation and expect that users will respond by rotating their device to match, but this can create problems. Some users have their devices mounted in a fixed orientation (e.g. on the arm of a power wheelchair). Therefore, websites and applications need to support both orientations by not restricting the orientation. Changes in content or functionality due to the size of display are not covered by this criterion, which is focused on restrictions of orientation.

How is the criterion met?

Content does not restrict its view and operation to a single display orientation, such as portrait or landscape, unless a specific display orientation is essential.

1.3.5 [Identify Input Purpose](#)

What is affected and why?

The purpose of the input fields that relate to the user himself should be programmatically determinable. Some people with cognitive disabilities may not understand the input's purpose from the label alone. In addition, autocomplete offers input suggestions for the field, which users can simply accept. This makes text entry easier.

How is the criterion met?

The HTML autocomplete attribute is currently suitable for this, with which the input purpose can be defined for fields such as name, e-mail or telephone number as well as for address data or credit card data. Alternatively, other supported taxonomies can specify the input purpose and replace the use of autocomplete. The respective taxonomies of [WCAG 2.1](#) should be adhered to.

Example:

The first picture shows a login field that is labeled with the corresponding autocomplete taxonomy in the source code that is shown in the following picture.

E-MAIL ADDRESS

```
<input type="email" name="email" value  
autocomplete="email" aria-label="E-mail address"  
required autofocus class="empty"> == $0
```

Guideline 1.4 Distinguishable

Make it easier for users to see and hear content, including separating foreground from background.

1.4.1 [Use of Color](#)

What is affected and why?

Color is an important asset in the design of web content, enhancing its aesthetic appeal, usability, and accessibility. However, some users have difficulty perceiving color. People with partial sight often experience limited color vision, and many older users do not see color well. In addition, people using limited-color or monochrome displays and browsers will be unable to access information that is presented only in color.

How is the criterion met?

Color is not used as the only visual means of conveying information, indicating an action, prompting a response, or distinguishing a visual element.

Example

1.4.2 [Audio Control](#)

What is affected and why?

Individuals who use screen reading software can find it hard to hear the speech output if there is other audio playing at the same time. This difficulty is exacerbated when the screen reader's speech output is software based (as most are today) and is controlled via the same volume control as the sound. Therefore, it is important that the user be able to turn off the background sound. Having control of the volume includes being able to reduce its volume to zero. Muting the system volume is not "pausing or stopping" the autoplay audio. Both the

"pause or stop" and control of audio volume need to be independent of the overall system volume.

How is the criterion met?

If any audio on a web page plays automatically for more than 3 seconds, either a mechanism is available to pause or stop the audio, or a mechanism is available to control audio volume independently of the overall system volume level.

1.4.3 [Contrast \(Minimum\)](#)

What is affected and why?

All texts on the page should have sufficient brightness contrasts in all states. Good contrasts ensure that users can read texts more easily. In particular, people who have reduced contrast sensitivity due to reduced visual acuity, color vision deficiency, or age benefit from good contrasts.

How is the criterion met?

The contrast ratio between foreground and background color is at least 4.5:1 for texts under 18 pt (or for bold texts under 14 pt). The contrast ratio between foreground and background color is at least 3:1 for texts in large font sizes (18 pt and larger, 14 pt and larger for bold fonts). If the requirement is only fulfilled via an alternative view, the style switcher itself fulfills the contrast requirement of 4.5:1 and other accessibility requirements.

Example:

The picture shows a text (16pt) which clearly meets the contrast specifications with 7.7:1.

1.4.4 [Resize Text](#)

What is affected and why?

The criterion refers to text on a website. Users should be able to adjust the font size according to their needs, while still being able to read the text and use the website. Moreover, some users rely on an increased text size on a web page.

How is the criterion met?

Text should be able to be enlarged by up to 200% without overlapping or truncated content and without impairing functionality. At least one of the following requirements must be met:

- the browser's zoom function can be used to enlarge the font to 200% (the page often changes to a new layout when this happens),
- the font size can be enlarged using a control element at the top of the page.

Example:

The picture shows a website that is still functional with a font enlarged to 200%.

1.4.5 [Images of Text](#)

What is affected and why?

Images of text means text that has been rendered in a non-text form (e.g. an image) in order to achieve a particular visual effect. The intent of this success criterion is to encourage authors, who are using technologies which are capable of achieving their desired default visual presentation, to enable people who require a particular visual presentation of text to be able to adjust the text presentation as needed. This includes people who require the text in a particular font size, foreground and background color, font family, line spacing or alignment.

How is the criterion met?

If the technologies being used can achieve the visual presentation, text is used to convey information rather than images of text except for the following:

- 1) customizable: the image of text can be visually customized to the user's requirements,
- 2) essential: a particular presentation of text is essential to the information being conveyed (e.g. text that is part of a logo or brand name).

1.4.10 [Reflow](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to let users enlarge text and other related content without having to scroll in two dimensions to read. When lines of text extend beyond the edge of a viewport, users will be forced to scroll back and forth to read line by line. This can cause them to lose their place and can significantly increase both physical and cognitive effort. Therefore, most sections of content are expected to reflow within the appropriate sizing requirement defined by this success criterion.

How is the criterion met?

Content can be presented without loss of information or functionality and without requiring scrolling in two dimensions for:

- vertical scrolling of content at a width equivalent to 320 CSS pixels, horizontal scrolling of content at a height equivalent to 256 CSS pixels.

An exception is made for parts of the content which require two-dimensional layout for usage or meaning.

1.4.11 [Non-Text Contrast](#)

What is affected and why?

The criterion refers to information-bearing graphic control elements that are active and not merely supplementary (e.g. to text) or information-bearing graphics. The test step is not applicable to photos, logos, flags, screenshots, diagrams with colors that may not be changed, and data visualizations with color gradations such as heat maps. Many people with visual impairments need good contrast in order to be able to perceive graphic controls or their statuses or elements in information-bearing graphics, such as statistical diagrams or charts.

How is the criterion met?

All visual information required by a user to identify that a control is present and how to operate it shall have a contrast ratio of at least 3:1 to the adjacent colors. Also, any visual information required to indicate the state, e.g. whether a component is selected or focused, must ensure that the information used to identify the control in that state has a contrast ratio of at least 3:1.

Example:

The picture shows a control element (arrow) which clearly meets the contrast specifications with 7.7:1.

1.4.12 [Text Spacing](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this is to ensure that when people override author-specified text spacing to improve their reading experience, content is still readable and operable. This focuses on the adaptability of content to a change in spacing between lines, words, letters, and paragraphs. Any combination of these may assist a user with effectively reading text. Ensuring that content correctly adapts when users override author settings for spacing also significantly increases the likelihood other style preferences can be set by the user. For example, a user may need to change to a wider font family than the author has set in order to effectively read text.

How is the criterion met?

In content implemented using markup languages that support the following text style properties, no loss of content or functionality occurs by setting all of the following and by changing no other style property:

- 1) Line height (line spacing) to at least 1.5 times the font size;
- 2) Spacing following paragraphs to at least 2 times the font size;
- 3) Letter spacing (tracking) to at least 0.12 times the font size;
- 4) Word spacing to at least 0.16 times the font size.

1.4.13 [Content on Hover or Focus](#)

What is affected and why?

Additional content that appears and disappears in coordination with keyboard focus or pointer hover often leads to accessibility issues. Examples of such interactions can include custom tooltips, sub-menus and other non-modal popups which display on hover and focus.

The intent of this success criterion is to ensure that authors who cause additional content to appear and disappear in this manner must design the interaction in such a way that users can perceive the additional content and dismiss it without disrupting their page experience.

How is the criterion met?

Where receiving and then removing pointer hover or keyboard focus triggers additional content to become visible and then hidden, the following are true:

- 1) Dismissible: A mechanism is available to dismiss the additional content without moving pointer hover or keyboard focus, unless the additional content communicates an input error or does not obscure or replace other content;
- 2) Hoverable: If pointer hover can trigger the additional content, then the pointer can be moved over the additional content without the additional content disappearing;
- 3) Persistent: The additional content remains visible until the hover or focus trigger is removed, the user dismisses it, or its information is no longer valid.

2. Operable

User interface components and navigation must be operable.

Guideline 2.1 Keyboard Accessible

All functionality of the content is operable through a keyboard interface without requiring specific timings for individual keystrokes (e.g. a specific speed or time-limit), except when the function itself depends on how the user moves (e.g., drawing or freehand gestures), not just on where the movement starts and ends.

2.1.1 [Keyboard](#)

What is affected and why?

If the website contains interactive elements, these must also be accessible via the keyboard. When content can be operated through a keyboard or an alternate keyboard, it is operable by people with no vision (who cannot use devices such as mice that require eye-hand coordination) as well as by people who must use alternate keyboards or input devices that act as keyboard emulators.

How is the criterion met?

In principle, all essential content and functions are accessible and operable without requiring specific timings for individual keystrokes, except where the underlying function requires input, that depends on the path of the user's movement and not just the endpoints. Sometimes something can look like an operating element, but it is not. However, as soon as it can be operated using the mouse, it must also be controllable using the keyboard or a keyboard alternative. For example, keyboard-controlled alternatives must also be offered for important operating functions that can be operated by drag-and-drop.

2.1.2 [No Keyboard Trap](#)

What is affected and why?

Operation should be possible regardless of the device. This means that it must be possible to use both the mouse and the keyboard. Many people with motor impairments or blind people, for example, are dependent on keyboard operation.

How is the criterion met?

If the keyboard focus can be moved to an element of the page, it must also be possible to move it away from this element again and it must be operable.

2.1.4 [Character Key Shortcuts](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to reduce accidental activation of keyboard shortcuts. Character key shortcuts work well for many keyboard users. However, they can be inappropriate and frustrating for speech input users, whose dictation is interpreted as strings of letters, and for keyboard users who are prone to accidentally hit keys. To rectify this issue, authors need to allow users to turn off or reconfigure shortcuts that are made up of only character keys.

How is the criterion met?

If a keyboard shortcut is implemented in content using only letter (including upper- and lower-case letters), punctuation, number, or symbol characters, then at least one of the following is true:

- 1) Turn off: A mechanism is available to turn the shortcut off;
- 2) Remap: A mechanism is available to remap the shortcut to include one or more non-printable keyboard keys (e.g. Ctrl, Alt);
- 3) Active only on focus: The keyboard shortcut for a user interface component is only active when that component has focus.

Guideline 2.2 Enough Time

Provide users enough time to read and use the content.

2.2.1 [Timing Adjustable](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to ensure that users with disabilities are given adequate time to interact with web content whenever possible. People with disabilities may require more time to read content or to perform functions such as filling out online forms. If web functions are time-dependent, it will be difficult for some users to perform the required action before a time limit occurs. This may render the service inaccessible to them.

How is the criterion met?

For each time limit that is set by the content, at least one of the following is true:

- **Turn off:** The user is allowed to turn off the time limit before encountering it; or

- **Adjust:** The user is allowed to adjust the time limit before encountering it over a wide range that is at least ten times the length of the default setting; or
- **Extend:** The user is warned before time expires and given at least 20 seconds to extend the time limit with a simple action (for example, "press the space bar"), and the user is allowed to extend the time limit at least ten times; or
- **Real-time Exception:** The time limit is a required part of a real-time event (for example, an auction), and no alternative to the time limit is possible; or
- **Essential Exception:** The time limit is essential, and extending it would invalidate the activity; or
- **20 Hour Exception:** The time limit is longer than 20 hours.

2.2.2 [Pause, Stop, Hide](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to avoid distracting users during their interaction with a web page. In the context of this success criterion, "starts automatically" broadly refers to animations/updates that are not the direct result of a user's intentional activation, for example, selecting a link or button. Content that moves or auto-updates can be a barrier to anyone who has trouble reading stationary text quickly, as well as anyone who has trouble tracking moving objects. It can also cause problems for screen readers. Moving content can also be a severe distraction for some people. Certain groups, particularly those with attention deficit disorders, find blinking content distracting, making it difficult for them to concentrate on other parts of the web page. Five seconds was chosen because it is long enough to get a user's attention, but not so long that a user cannot wait out the distraction if necessary to use the page.

How is the criterion met?

For moving, blinking, scrolling, or auto-updating information, all of the following are true:

- **Moving, blinking, scrolling:**
For any moving, blinking or scrolling information that (1) starts automatically, (2) lasts more than five seconds, and (3) is presented in parallel with other content, there is a mechanism for the user to pause, stop, or hide it unless the movement, blinking, or scrolling is part of an activity where it is essential; and
- **Auto-updating:**
For any auto-updating information that (1) starts automatically and (2) is presented in parallel with other content, there is a mechanism for the user to pause, stop, or hide it or to control the frequency of the update unless the auto-updating is part of an activity where it is essential.

2.3.1 [Three Flashes or Below Threshold](#)

What is affected and why?

Since any content that does not meet this success criterion can interfere with a user's ability to use the whole page, all content on the web page must meet this success criterion. People with epilepsy are particularly at risk because prolonged flickering at certain frequencies can trigger a seizure.

How is the criterion met?

The page does not contain any elements that flash more than three times in a period of one second.

2.4.1 [Bypass Blocks](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to allow people who navigate sequentially through content more direct access to the primary content of the web page. Web pages and applications often have content that appears on other pages or screens. Examples of repeated blocks of content include but are not limited to navigation links, header content, and advertising frames. Small repeated sections such as individual words, phrases or single links are not considered blocks for the purposes of this provision. Users who navigate sequentially through content will generally have to navigate through repeated content on each page. This is in contrast to a sighted user's ability to ignore the repeated material either by focusing on the center of the screen (where main content usually appears) or a mouse user's ability to select a link with a single mouse click rather than encountering every link or form control that comes before the item they want.

How is the criterion met?

A mechanism is available to bypass blocks of content that are repeated on multiple web pages.

2.4.2 [Page Titled](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to help users find content and orient themselves within it by ensuring that each web page has a descriptive title. Titles identify the current location without requiring users to read or interpret page content. When titles appear in site maps or lists of search results, users can more quickly identify the content they need. User agents make the title of the page easily available to the user for identifying the page. For instance, a user agent may display the page title in the window title bar or as the name of the tab containing the page.

How is the criterion met?

Web pages have titles that describe their topic or purpose.

2.4.3 Focus Order

What is affected and why?

Web pages with links, form elements, or objects should be keyboard accessible. If the focus sequence is not comprehensible, users using the keyboard run the risk of losing their bearings and keyboard operability can be significantly impaired as a result.

How is the criterion met?

When the website is operated using the keyboard, the order in which links, form elements and objects are accessed should be logical and comprehensible.

Example:

The picture shows the order of the keyboard steps.

2.4.4 Link Purpose

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to help users understand the purpose of each link so they can decide whether they want to follow the link. Whenever possible, provide link text

that identifies the purpose of the link without needing additional context. Assistive technology has the ability to provide users with a list of links that are on the web page. Link text that is as meaningful as possible will aid users who want to choose from this list of links. Meaningful link text also helps those who wish to tab from link to link. Meaningful links help users choose which links to follow without requiring complicated strategies to understand the page.

How is the criterion met?

The purpose of each link can be determined from the link text alone or from the link text together with its programmatically determined link context, except where the purpose of the link would be ambiguous to users in general.

2.4.5 [Multiple Ways](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to make it possible for users to locate content in a manner that best meets their needs. Users may find one technique easier or more comprehensible to use than another. Even small sites should provide users with some means of orientation. For a very small website (like one with only 3 or 4 pages), where every single page can be reached directly from the main "Home" page, it may be sufficient simply to provide links from and to the home page where the links on the home page can also serve as a site map.

How is the criterion met?

There should be more than one way to locate a web page within a set of web pages—such as using a search function, a sitemap, or menu navigation. This does not apply to pages that are the result of, or a step in, a process (e.g., filling out a form or completing a checkout).

2.4.6 [Headings and Labels](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to help users understand what information is contained in web pages and how that information is organized. When headings are clear and descriptive, users can find the information they seek more easily, and they can understand the relationships between different parts of the content more easily. Descriptive labels help users identify specific components within the content.

How is the criterion met?

Headings and labels describe the topic or purpose of a web page.

2.4.7 [Focus Visible](#)

What is affected and why?

Keyboard users rely on a visible indication of where the keyboard focus is on the page—for example, which button will be activated when they press Enter, or which input field is currently selected. If the focus indicator is not clearly visible, it becomes difficult or impossible for users who navigate by keyboard to interact with the content effectively. To ensure accessibility, the keyboard focus must be clearly highlighted. If authors choose not to implement a custom focus style, the browser's default focus indication must not be removed or hidden using CSS. Any visible focus indicator (such as an outline, underline, or color change) must have a contrast ratio of at least 3:1 against the unfocused state, so that it is easy to distinguish. The focus indicator must not be time-limited - when the keyboard focus is shown it must remain.

How is the criterion met?

Any keyboard-operable user interface has a mode of operation where the keyboard focus indicator is visible.

2.5.1 [Pointer Gestures](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to ensure that content can be controlled with a range of pointing devices, abilities, and assistive technologies. Some people cannot perform gestures in a precise manner, or they may use a specialized or adapted input device such as a head pointer, eye-gaze system, or speech-controlled mouse emulator. Some pointing methods lack the capability or accuracy to perform multipoint or path-based gestures. Examples of path-based gestures include swiping, sliders and carousels dependent on the direction of interaction, and other gestures which trace a prescribed path, such as drawing a specific shape. Such paths may be drawn with a finger or stylus on a touchscreen, graphics tablet, or trackpad, or with a mouse, joystick, or similar pointer device.

How is the criterion met?

All functionality that uses multipoint or path-based gestures for operation can be operated with a single pointer without a path-based gesture, unless a multipoint or path-based gesture is essential.

2.5.2 [Pointer Cancellation](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to make it easier for users to prevent accidental or erroneous pointer input. People with various disabilities can inadvertently initiate touch or mouse events with unwanted results. Each of the following subsections roughly aligns with the bullets of this success criterion, and outlines a means of allowing users to cancel pointer operations.

How is the criterion met?

For functionality that can be operated using a single pointer, at least one of the following is true:

- No Down-Event: The down-event of the pointer is not used to execute any part of the function;
- Abort or Undo: Completion of the function is on the up-event, and a mechanism is available to abort the function before completion or to undo the function after completion;
- Up Reversal: The up-event reverses any outcome of the preceding down-event;
- Essential: Completing the function on the down-event is essential.

2.5.3 [Label in Name](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to ensure that the words which visually label a component are also the words associated with the component programmatically. This helps ensure that people with disabilities can rely on visible labels as a means to interact with the components.

How is the criterion met?

For user interface components with labels that include text or images of text, the name contains the text that is presented visually.

Log in to Systems

2.5.4 [Motion Actuation](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to ensure that functions triggered by moving a device (for example shaking or tilting) or by gesturing towards the device (so that sensors like a camera can pick up and interpret the gesturing), can also be operated by more conventional user interface components.

Devices often have sensors that can act as inputs, such as accelerometer and gyroscope sensors on a phone or tablet device. These sensors can allow the user to control something by simply changing the orientation or moving the device in particular ways. In other situations, web content can interpret user gestures via the camera or other sensors to actuate functions. For example, shaking the device might issue an "Undo" command, or a gentle hand wave might be used to move forward or backward in a sequence of pages. Some users with disabilities are not able to operate these device sensors (either not at all, or not precisely enough) because the device is on a fixed mount (perhaps a wheelchair) or due to motor impairments. Therefore, functionality offered through motion must also be available by another mechanism.

How is the criterion met?

Functionality that can be operated by device motion or user motion can also be operated by user interface components and responding to the motion can be disabled to prevent accidental actuation. This does not apply if the motion is used via an accessibility-supported interface or if the motion is essential to the functionality and cannot be replaced without fundamentally changing the user experience.

3. Understandable

Information and the operation of the user interface must be understandable.

Guideline 3.1 Readable

Make text content readable and understandable.

3.1.1 [Language of Page](#)

What is affected and why?

The purpose of this success criterion is to ensure that web developers include information in their pages that helps user agents display text and language content correctly. Both assistive technologies and conventional user agents can render text more accurately when the language of the web page is identified. Screen readers can load the correct pronunciation rules. Visual browsers can display characters and scripts correctly. Media players can show captions correctly. As a result, users with disabilities will be better able to understand the content.

How is the criterion met?

The default human language of each web page can be programmatically determined (based on information added by the author in a way that different tools—including those for people with disabilities—can read and use to show or speak the content to users).

3.1.2 [Language of Parts](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to ensure that user agents can correctly present phrases, passages, and in some cases words written in multiple languages. This makes it possible for user agents and assistive technologies to present content according to the presentation and pronunciation rules for that language. This applies to graphical browsers as well as screen readers, braille displays, and other voice browsers.

Both assistive technologies and conventional user agents can render text more accurately if the language of each passage of text is identified. Screen readers can use the pronunciation rules of the language of the text. Visual browsers can display characters and scripts in appropriate ways. This is especially important when switching between languages that read from left to right and languages that read from right to left, or when text is rendered in a language that uses a different alphabet. Users with disabilities who know all the languages

used in the web page will be better able to understand the content when each passage is rendered appropriately.

How is the criterion met?

The human language of each passage or phrase in the content can be programmatically determined except for proper names, technical terms, words of indeterminate language, and words or phrases if they have found their way into the respective linguistic usage. Mixed words (e.g. Webauftritt, Checkpunkt) should also not be labelled.

Guideline 3.2 Predictable

Make web pages appear and operate in predictable ways.

3.2.1 [On Focus](#)

What is affected and why?

The criterion applies to any user interface component that receives focus. Unexpected and unannounced context changes when focusing on a component can affect the orientation of users. For example, if a form is submitted automatically when a user tabs to a component, they may be redirected to a new page without warning, disrupting their workflow and causing confusion. Context changes on the page itself can distract and confuse users or go unnoticed and thus cause confusion.

How is the criterion met?

If any component of the page receives the focus, this should not lead to an unexpected context change (such as pop-up windows or automatic submission of forms). Opening custom tooltips, i.e. non-modal windows that close automatically when you continue to tab or click with the mouse, is not considered a context change.

3.2.2 [On Input](#)

What is affected and why?

The criterion applies to pages with interactive buttons or form elements. Context changes on the page itself can distract and confuse users or go unnoticed and thus cause confusion (e.g. content is suddenly changed). They should therefore be announced and clearly comprehensible. If changes on the same page do not take place below the element that triggers them, they are often not noticed by blind users.

How is the criterion met?

User input on forms should not lead to unexpected context changes. All context changes must be made below the triggering element and should be clearly traceable and the focus should not be shifted.

3.2.3 [Consistent Navigation](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to encourage the use of consistent presentation and layout for users who interact with repeated content within a set of web pages and need to locate specific information or functionality more than once. Individuals with low vision who use screen magnification to display a small portion of the screen at a time often use visual cues and page boundaries to quickly locate repeated content. Presenting repeated content in the same order is also important for visual users, who use spatial memory or visual cues within the design to locate repeated content.

How is the criterion met?

Navigational mechanisms that are repeated on multiple web pages within a set of web pages occur in the same relative order each time they are repeated, unless a change is initiated by the user.

3.2.4 [Consistent Identification](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to ensure consistent identification of functional components that appear repeatedly within a set of web pages. A strategy of people using screen readers when operating a website is to rely heavily on their familiarity with functions that may appear on different web pages. If identical functions have different labels (or, more generally, a different accessible name) on different web pages, the site will be considerably more difficult to use. It may also be confusing and increase the cognitive load for people with cognitive limitations. Therefore, consistent labeling will help.

How is the criterion met?

Components that have the same functionality within a set of web pages are identified consistently.

3.3.1 [Error Identification](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to ensure that users are aware that an error has occurred and can determine what is wrong. In the case of an unsuccessful form submission, it is not sufficient to only re-display the form without providing any hint that the submission failed. The error must be indicated in text.

How is the criterion met?

If an input error is automatically detected, the item that is in error is identified and the error is described to the user in text.

3.3.2 [Labels or Instructions](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to have content authors present instructions or labels that identify the controls in a form so that users know what input data is expected. In the case of radio buttons, checkboxes, comboboxes, or similar controls that provide users with

options, each option must have an appropriate label so that users know what they are actually selecting. Instructions or labels may also specify data formats for data entry fields, especially if they are out of the customary formats or if there are specific rules for correct input. Content authors may also choose to make such instructions available to users only when the individual control has focus, especially when instructions are long and verbose.

How is the criterion met?

Labels or instructions are provided when content requires user input.

3.3.3 [Error Suggestion](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to ensure that users receive appropriate suggestions for correction of an input error if it is possible. The definition of "input error" says that it is "information provided by the user that is not accepted" by the system. Some examples of information that is not accepted include information that is required but omitted by the user and information that is provided by the user, but that falls outside the required data format or allowed values.

How is the criterion met?

If an input error is automatically detected and suggestions for correction are known, then the suggestions are provided to the user, unless it would jeopardize the security or purpose of the content.

3.3.4 [Error Prevention \(Legal, Financial, Data\)](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to help users with disabilities avoid serious consequences as the result of a mistake when performing an action that cannot be reversed. For example, purchasing non-refundable airline tickets or submitting an order to purchase stock in a brokerage account are financial transactions with serious consequences. If users have made a mistake on the date of air travel, they could end up with a ticket for the wrong day that cannot be exchanged. If users made a mistake on the number of stock shares to be purchased, they could end up purchasing more stock than intended. Both of these types of mistakes involve transactions that take place immediately and cannot be altered afterward, and can be very costly. Likewise, it may be an unrecoverable error if users unintentionally modify or delete data stored in a database that they later need to access, such as their entire travel profile in a travel services website. When referring to modification or deletion of "user controllable" data, the intent is to prevent mass loss of data such as deleting a file or record. It is not the intent to require a confirmation for each save command or the simple creation or editing of documents, records or other data.

Users with disabilities may be more likely to make mistakes. People with reading disabilities may transpose numbers and letters, and those with motor disabilities may hit keys by mistake. Providing the ability to reverse actions allows users to correct a mistake that could result in serious consequences. Providing the ability to review and correct information gives

the user an opportunity to detect a mistake before taking an action that has serious consequences.

How is the criterion met?

For web pages that cause legal commitments or financial transactions for the user to occur, that modify or delete user-controllable data in data storage systems, or that submit user test responses, at least one of the following is true:

- Reversible: Submissions are reversible.
- Checked: Data entered by the user is checked for input errors and the user is provided an opportunity to correct them.
- Confirmed: A mechanism is available for reviewing, confirming, and correcting information before finalizing the submission.

4. Robust

4.1.1 [Parsing](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to ensure that user agents, including assistive technologies, can accurately interpret and parse content. If the content cannot be parsed into a data structure, then different user agents may present it differently or be completely unable to parse it. Some user agents use "repair techniques" to render poorly coded content. Since repair techniques vary among user agents, authors cannot assume that content will be accurately parsed into a data structure or that it will be rendered correctly by specialized user agents, including assistive technologies, unless the content is created according to the rules defined in the formal grammar for that technology. In markup languages, errors in element and attribute syntax and failure to provide properly nested start/end tags lead to errors that prevent user agents from parsing the content reliably. Therefore, the success criterion requires that the content can be parsed using only the rules of the formal grammar.

How is the criterion met?

In content implemented using markup languages, elements have complete start and end tags, elements are nested according to their specifications, elements do not contain duplicate attributes, and any IDs are unique, except where the specifications allow these features.

4.1.2 [Name, Role, Value](#)

What is affected and why?

This success criterion ensures that AT can recognize, control, and stay updated on the status of UI components. When standard, accessible UI controls are used correctly, AT can interact with them easily. However, if custom controls are created or existing elements are given new roles through code, developers must provide extra information to make these controls accessible. This includes ensuring AT can detect the control's role (like button or checkbox),

its current state (such as selected or collapsed), and whether it has keyboard focus. These states must be communicated programmatically so AT can respond appropriately.

How is the criterion met?

For all user interface components (including but not limited to: form elements, links and components generated by scripts), the name and role can be programmatically determined; states, properties, and values that can be set by the user can be programmatically set; and notification of changes to these items is available to user agents, including assistive technologies.

4.1.3 [Status Messages](#)

What is affected and why?

The intent of this success criterion is to make users aware of important changes in content that are not given focus, and to do so in a way that doesn't unnecessarily interrupt their work. The intended beneficiaries are blind and low vision users of assistive technologies with screen reader capabilities. An additional benefit is that assistive technologies for users with cognitive disabilities may achieve an alternative means of indicating (or even delaying or suppressing) status messages, as preferred by the user.

How is the criterion met?

In content implemented using markup languages, status messages can be programmatically determined through role or properties such that they can be presented to the user by assistive technologies without receiving focus.

4. Accessibility Best Practices for Development

Early Integration of Accessibility

The guiding principle is simple: the earlier accessibility is considered, the better. Retrofitting accessibility criteria afterward is almost always more time-consuming—and therefore more expensive. For example, if a color scheme is developed from the start in compliance with contrast requirements, there is no need to rework finalized designs at greater cost.

Choosing Technologies

At the very start of the project, you must decide which programming language, development environment, or software to use. As a general rule, rely on standard web technologies: HTML, CSS, and JavaScript form a stable platform for accessible web content and application development, provided they are used in accordance with established standards. Conforming to standards ensures that assistive technologies and browsers alike have the best chance of rendering content accessible and correctly.

- HTML should be used according to its specifications to convey structure and meaning.
- CSS controls visual presentation across different screen resolutions and contexts (for example, printing).

- JavaScript provides interactivity when HTML alone is insufficient.
- If you incorporate other web technologies, do so thoughtfully and only when appropriate.

In any case, investigate in advance in removing any accessibility limitations or in establishing the support structures of the technology or software you are considering. Moreover, inform yourself about special accessibility guidelines, for example, those published by Oracle, Microsoft, IBM, or for languages such as Java or C#. When using a third-party UI library (e.g. Bootstrap, jQuery UI, Angular), consult its documentation to understand built-in accessibility support and to identify areas where you must add missing support.

Using Third-Party Tools

In scenarios where basic services incorporate third-party tools that are public-facing, these parts have to meet the same legal requirements. While these tools can be powerful and flexible, their accessibility should never be assumed. Just because a tool is open source or widely used does not guarantee it meets WCAG 2.1 Level AA requirements.

Therefore, when selecting or integrating external tools, whether for front-end interfaces, content management, or service delivery, the teams should evaluate their accessibility features and limitations early. This is especially important if the tools are user-facing or an interactive part of the user experience. You can find important guidance and practical advice on how to evaluate software and services—which can support you in selecting appropriate tools and methods—in the document “Service Evaluation Guide” (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15720404>).

If a tool lacks full accessibility, consider: Whether adaptations can be implemented by yourself or the provider,

- If an accessible alternative exists,
- Or, as a last resort, whether the tool can be used with appropriate disclaimers and mitigation strategies (e.g., documenting known issues, providing support channels, and information about this in the Accessibility Statement)

Normally, open source tools offer more opportunities to make changes independently and avoid expensive adaptations by the provider. If possible, the issue of accessibility is already taken into account when concluding contracts with providers, so that the costs are borne by the provider in case of doubt if accessibility problems are identified.

Defining Requirements

During the requirement analysis phase, include WCAG 2.1 Level AA criteria, and any other relevant accessibility standards in your requirements catalog. Specifying these criteria early helps ensure they become an integral part of planning and design. For further important

design aspects, Base4NFDI will provide guidance in a comprehensive Service Design Guide (soon accessible under <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16306727>)

Ongoing Testing and Validation

Throughout service development, regular automated scans with testing tools can provide a rough analysis of your accessibility status and help you react promptly. However, it is also advisable to conduct at least one manual review against the full criteria catalog.

Guidance on how to perform these checks can be found in chapter 3 or in the respective [WCAG criteria](#). In addition, the selection of the so-called knock-out criteria helps with prioritization in terms of planning, implementation and improvement. The entire [BITV 2.0 test steps](#) are also described in detail in German by DIAS GmbH. On the same web page, you will find various [bookmarklets](#) and links to screen readers that make manual testing easier.

It is also useful to familiarize yourself with screen readers to be able to test and also better understand the experience of users who rely on them. Moreover, test your code with a variety of assistive-technology and browser combinations. Browsers differ slightly in how they support HTML and CSS features; the same applies to assistive technologies, especially screen readers. As a result, the user experience may vary depending on interactivity and implementation. Begin testing on the most common platforms, for example:

- Windows: JAWS with Internet Explorer and Firefox; NVDA with Firefox
- macOS: VoiceOver with Safari

By integrating these practices from the outset, you will reduce rework, control costs, and deliver a truly accessible user experience.

5. Appendices

I Links to Tools & Resources:

Web Developer Toolbar

Supports the implementation of the individual test steps of the WCAG criteria.

- Firefox: <https://addons.mozilla.org/de/firefox/addon/web-developer/>
- Chrome: https://chrome.google.com/webstore/detail/web-developer/bfbameneiokkkgbdmiekhi_nmfkcndhdm?hl=de

WAVE

Suitable for checking the accessibility of a web page. Wave displays various icons in the original website and thus shows potential accessibility problems.

- Firefox: <https://addons.mozilla.org/en-US/firefox/addon/wave-accessibility-tool/>
- Chrome: <https://chrome.google.com/webstore/detail/wave-evaluation-tool/jbbplnjkjmeebjpjjfedlgcdilocofh>
- Usage:
 - 1) to run a WAVE report, simply click on the WAVE icon to the right of your browser's address bar. Click the icon again or refresh the page to remove the WAVE interface.
 - 2) You can also trigger a WAVE report by pressing Ctrl + Shift + U (Command + Shift + U on Mac) or by activating the context menu item "WAVE this page" (right-click).

Accessibility Insights for Web

Suitable for automated accessibility checking and checking whether a web application or website complies with the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.1 Level

- Chrome: <https://chrome.google.com/webstore/detail/accessibility-insights-fo/pbjikliggfmaakdaogkfomddhfmjni>
- Microsoft Edge: <https://microsoftedge.microsoft.com/addons/detail/accessibility-insights-fo/ghbhpcokfemncgoinjblecnilppimih>
- For Windows and Android: <https://accessibilityinsights.io/downloads>
- Applicability: The tool supports two main scenarios:
 - FastPass is an easy, two-step process that allows developers to identify common high-accessibility issues in less than five minutes.
 - Automated checks - The tool automatically checks that approximately 50 accessibility requirements are met.
 - Tabs - The tool provides clear instructions and a visual helper to easily identify critical accessibility issues related to keyboard access such as missing tabs, keyboard traps and incorrect tab order.
 - The assessment allows anyone with HTML knowledge to check whether a web application or website complies with the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.1 Level AA.
 - Automated checks - The tool automatically checks whether approximately 50 accessibility requirements are met.
 - Manual tests - The tool provides step-by-step instructions, examples and troubleshooting guides for approximately 20 tests. Many tests are "assisted", which means that the tool identifies the test instances or provides a visual helper.

ARC Toolkit

The ARC Toolkit is a set of accessibility tools that developers can use to identify accessibility issues and features for WCAG 2.0, WCAG 2.1, EN 301 549 and Section 508.

- Chrome:
<https://chrome.google.com/webstore/detail/arc-toolkit/chdkkkccnlfncngelccgbgmjebmkmce>
- Firefox: Unfortunately not found

Siteimprove Accessibility Checker

The Siteimprove Accessibility Checker is your tool to check any website for accessibility issues at any time. It gives you intuitive, visual feedback on your content by highlighting identified issues directly on the page and giving you an instant overview of your site's accessibility issues, a clear explanation of how they affect your users and specific recommendations on how to fix them.

- Firefox: <https://addons.mozilla.org/en-US/firefox/addon/digital-certainty-index/>
- Chrome:
<https://chrome.google.com/webstore/detail/siteimprove-accessibility/efcfolpjhicnikpmhnmphjhpiclljc>

Color Contrast Analyser

For flexible checking of contrasts. Can be used on websites, in app development, when designing graphics for social media, PowerPoint slides, PDFs, etc. It also classifies contrast according to the WCAG standard.

- Free download at: <https://www.tpgi.com/color-contrast-checker/>

NVDA Screen Reader

It is an open-source screen reader for Windows that is used in particular to support the checking of dynamic web content (in combination with Firefox). NVDA is considered to be largely standards-compliant and is therefore better suited for checking correct markup than the screen reader JAWS, for example, which compensates for some errors in the markup.

- Free download at: <https://www.nvaccess.org/download/>

II References:

1. **Barrierefreiheitsstärkungsgesetz (BFSG) – German Accessibility Act**

- Official German government page: [BFSG](#)
- 2. Bundesteilhabegesetz (BGG) – Federal Disability Equality Act**
 - Official German government page: BGG. Retrieved April 30, 2025, from [BGG](#)
- 3. European Accessibility Act (EAA) – EU Regulations**
 - European Commission: [EU Accessibility Act Overview](#)
- 4. WCAG 2.1 AA Guidelines – Web Accessibility Standard**
 - W3C Official Guidelines: [WCAG 2.1 AA](#)

III Accessibility Statement Template

Note: This is a general accessibility statement template aligned with EU and national accessibility requirements, including the **Austrian model accessibility statement**. The template incorporates best practices from EU-wide accessibility laws, such as the **European Accessibility Act (EAA)**, and national regulations like **Germany's BGG** and **BITV 2.0**. The Austrian reference was used for the framework of the statement, serving as a model for creating accessible digital services in line with legal obligations and standards.

Before publishing, please adapt it to your service's specific situation, including the actual accessibility status, evaluation method, contact information, and the appropriate enforcement body based on your legal jurisdiction.

Accessibility Statement for [Service Name]

This accessibility statement applies to the digital service “[Service Name]” available at [https://service-url.example].

Commitment to Accessibility

We are committed to ensuring digital accessibility for all users, including people with disabilities. We strive to continuously improve usability and accessibility in accordance with applicable legal requirements and best practices.

Development Status

[Service Name] is currently in [active development / pre-release/early stages]. We are actively working to ensure full accessibility and will continue to improve the service's accessibility as development progresses. At this time, some areas of the service may not yet be fully accessible.

Compliance Status

This website is [fully / partially / not] compliant with the **Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.1**, Level AA, and conforms to the requirements of **Directive (EU) 2016/2102** as implemented by **the German Accessibility Act (BGG)** and **Barrierefreie-Informationstechnik-Verordnung (BITV 2.0)**.

Preparation of This Accessibility Statement

This statement was prepared on [DD Month YYYY].

The assessment of accessibility was based on:

[Choose one or more]

- A self-assessment by the service provider
- An external audit conducted by [Name of Auditor]
- Automated testing tools

The statement was last reviewed on **[DD Month YYYY]**.

Known Accessibility Limitations

We are aware of the following accessibility issues:

- [Example: Certain documents are not available in accessible formats]
- [Example: Some user interface elements may not be fully navigable by keyboard]

We are actively working on addressing these issues as part of our ongoing development.

Feedback and Contact Information

If you notice any issues not listed here or require information in a different format, please contact us:

Contact for Accessibility Issues:

[Name or Unit]

Email: [accessibility@service.de]

Phone: [+49-XXXX-XXXXXX]

We aim to respond to accessibility feedback within **[X working days]**.

Enforcement Procedure

If you do not receive a satisfactory response, you may contact the designated enforcement body in accordance with the **German Accessibility Act (BGG)**:

Schlichtungsstelle für Barrierefreiheit

Federal Government Ombudsman for Digital Accessibility

[Website of the Ombudsman]

[Contact Details of Ombudsman]

For further legal guidance or unresolved complaints, you may also contact the responsible regional authority.

III Checklist of Accessibility Review

Note: The criteria below include the 24 criteria given by the Berlin administration. This checklist should be used as an initial assessment. Services should aim to fulfill all criteria covered above.

A self-rating scale from 1 to 3, with values assigned as:

- 1 – Basic Compliance (major issues or minimal implementation)
- 2 – Partial Compliance (mostly meets the requirement but needs improvement)
- 3 – Full Compliance (fully meets the requirement with no known issues)

Criteria	Summary	Compliance Rating (1–3)
1.1.1 Non-text Content	Provide text alternatives for any non-text content so it can be converted into other formats.	
1.2.1 Audio-only and Video-only (Prerecorded)	Provide alternatives such as transcripts or descriptions for audio- or video-only content.	
1.2.2 Captions (Prerecorded)	Include captions for all prerecorded audio content in synchronized media.	
1.2.3 Audio Description or Media Alternative (Prerecorded)	Provide audio descriptions or a full text alternative for video content.	
1.3.1 Info and Relationships	Use markup to convey relationships and structure (e.g. headings, lists).	
1.3.2 Meaningful Sequence	Present content in a logical order for screen readers and keyboard users.	
1.3.3 Sensory Characteristics	Avoid relying only on visual cues like color, shape, or location.	
1.3.5 Identify Input Purpose	Use appropriate autocomplete attributes to identify the purpose of fields.	

1.4.1 Use of Color	Don't rely on color alone to convey meaning or status.	
1.4.3 Contrast (Minimum)	Ensure text and interface elements meet minimum contrast ratios.	
1.4.4 Resize Text	Make sure text can be resized up to 200% without breaking layout.	
1.4.11 Non-text Contrast	Provide sufficient contrast for UI elements and graphics (min. 3:1).	
2.1.1 Keyboard	All functionality must be accessible via keyboard.	
2.1.2 No Keyboard Trap	Users must be able to exit any component using keyboard alone.	
2.2.1 Timing Adjustable	Let users extend or disable time limits.	
2.3.1 Three Flashes or Below Threshold	Avoid flashing content that could trigger seizures.	
2.4.3 Focus Order	Focus should move in a logical, expected order.	
2.4.4 Link Purpose (In Context)	Ensure links are clearly described and understandable.	
2.4.7 Focus Visible	Provide a clear visual indicator for keyboard focus.	
2.5.3 Label in Name	The visible label should be included in the accessible name.	
3.2.1 On Focus	Avoid unexpected changes when elements receive focus.	
3.2.2 On Input	Input fields shouldn't trigger major context changes unless warned.	

3.3.2 Labels or Instructions	Clearly label and guide users through form fields.	
4.1.2 Name, Role, Value	UI components must expose name, role, and value to assistive tech.	

Scoring:

65-72	Excellent (Compliant)	Meets or exceeds most accessibility guidelines; ready for formal audits or public accessibility claims.
55-64	High (Mostly Compliant)	Meets or exceeds most accessibility guidelines; ready for formal audits or public accessibility claims.
45-54	Moderate (Partially Compliant)	Some significant gaps exist; requires focused remediation in multiple areas.
35-44	Low (Minimally Compliant)	Basic effort has been made, but there are major accessibility deficiencies.
24-34	Very Low (Non-Compliant)	Substantial issues across most areas; not accessible to users with disabilities.